

Equilibrium uptake and sorption dynamics for the retrieval of divalent zinc from aqueous solutions using *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum*[†]

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Abstract : Biosorptive removal of divalent zinc from aqueous solution by using *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* was investigated in batch mode and the observations were correlated with the pH change, agitation time, dose of the adsorbent and initial concentration of metal ions in the solution. Biosorbent *Carissa carandas* leaf powder showed higher sorption efficiency than that of biosorbent *Syzygium aromaticum* powder under identical experimental conditions. Based on regression coefficient (R^2) values, the experimental data for adsorption of Zn^{II} on to *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* powder indicate that the Langmuir adsorption isotherm shows a better fit with the experimental data observed in this study compared with the Freundlich isotherm.

Keywords : Green chemistry, heavy metal, zinc, adsorption, biosorption, *Carissa carandas*, *Syzygium aromaticum*, Langmuir isotherm, Freundlich isotherm.

Introduction

Water pollution has become a global problem. The growth of industrial activities and the increasing water usage worldwide have led to the release of various pollutants into an aquatic environment, like heavy metals^{1,2}. Heavy metals, such as nickel, zinc, copper, cadmium, lead, mercury, cobalt and arsenic often presented in industrial wastewaters are hazardous to the aquatic ecosystem and pose possible human health risk³⁻⁵.

Zinc is also an essential element required for body growth, higher consumption causes many dangerous disease like nausea and vomiting in children, anemia and cholesterol problems in human beings⁶⁻⁸. According to the US Environmental Protection Agency, zinc is a major used metal and discharged in to the environment and its permissible limit for drinking water is 5 mg/L⁷.

Several different techniques used for the removal of Zn^{II} ions includes precipitation/coagulation⁹, chemical oxidation, biodegradation, adsorption, ion exchange¹⁰, membrane processing, electrolytic methods etc.⁴. Although these are efficient processes, they have disadvantages when used in industrial waste conformed by diluted metallic solu-

tions. Furthermore, these processes are expensive in terms of energy and chemical products consumption. Biosorption has been now recognized as an effective alternate method for removal of Zn^{II} from aqueous solutions. Many biosorbent are used for removal of heavy metals from water and waste water like rice husk^{11,12}, *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum*^{13,14}, wheat straw¹⁵, Cedar leaf¹⁶ and *Calotropis procera* Roots¹⁷.

The present study emphasizes on the use *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* in the removal of zinc(II) from aqueous solution. The study also include fitting of isotherms and kinetics studies.

Experimental work

Materials and methods :

Chemicals :

Analytical grade chemicals were used in this work without further purification. To avoid any interference of other ions, all solutions were prepared using double distilled water. To evaluate the significant of the adsorbent, stock solutions (1000 mg/L) of Zn^{II} was prepared by dissolving $ZnSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ in 1000 mL volumetric flask and make up

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

to the mark with double distilled water. All the required working solutions were prepared by diluting the stock solution with double distilled water. Dilute solutions of 0.1 M HNO₃ and 0.1 M NaOH were used to adjust pH of metal ion solutions using a pH meter.

Adsorbents :

The leaves of *Carissa carandas* and buds of *Syzygium aromaticum* were collected from local field of Pushkar (India) and from local market of Jaipur (India), respectively. These were washed with distilled water, dried in sunlight, then 60 °C for 24 h in hot air oven. Finally, the dried leaves of *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* were grinded in clean electric mixer and stored in a dry and clean plastic bag.

Experimental

Batch adsorption studies were performed at room temperature. The adsorption equilibrium experiments for Zn^{II} solution were carried out by taking 100 mL of zinc(II) solution in 250 mL conical flask. After a defined time interval of 60 min, samples were withdrawn from the shaker, filtered by Whatman filter paper No. 41 and the supernatant solutions were analyzed for Zn^{II} ion concentration using an Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (Thermo scientific Solar S-series AA Spectrometer). The removal of zinc was calculated according to following expression :

$$\text{Metal removal \%} = \frac{(C_i - C_f)}{C_0} \times 100$$

where C_i and C_f are the initial and equilibrium concentrations (mg/L).

The isothermal studies also calculated. The well-known expression of Langmuir isotherm model (Langmuir 1918) is presented as :

$$q_e = Q_0 b C_e / (1 + b C_e) \tag{1}$$

where, C_e (mg/L) and q_e (mg/g) are the liquid phase concentration and solid phase concentration of adsorbate at equilibrium, respectively and Q₀ (mg/g) and b (L/mg) are the Langmuir isotherm constants. The well-known expression for the Freundlich isotherm model (Freundlich 1907) is given as :

$$q_e = K_F C_e^n \tag{2}$$

where, K_F [mg/g (L/g)^{1/n}] is the Freundlich constant related to the bonding energy, n is the heterogeneity factor.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH on biosorption :

To study the effect of pH on adsorption of Zn^{II} ions, the batch equilibrium studies at pH values in the range of 2–10 were carried out. The results are furnished and presented in Fig. 1. Metal sorption is critically linked with pH and the effect of pH of the solution is a very important controlling factor in the adsorption process¹⁵. For this the role of hydrogen ion concentration was examined at different pH. The effect of pH was studied at the Zn^{II} concentration of 100 mg/L, biosorbent dosage of 2 g/100 mL at the pH range 2–10. It was observed that with the increase in the pH of the solution the percentage removal of Zn^{II} increased up to the pH 8 for *Carissa carandas* and pH 6 for *Syzygium aromaticum*.

Effect of contact time on biosorption :

The rate of biosorption is important for designing batch biosorption experiments. As shown in Fig. 2 the biosorption efficiency of Zn^{II} increased considerably until the contact time reached 180 min. Further increase in contact time did not enhance the biosorption, so, the optimum contact time was selected as 180 min for further experiments. The Zn^{II} adsorption rate at the initial stage may be explained by an increased availability in the number of active binding sites on the adsorbent surface¹⁶. The sorption rapidly occurs and normally controlled by the diffusion process from the bulk to the surface. In this later stage, no sorption takes place due to non-availability of sorption sites. The equilibrium time was independent of adsorbent type. Therefore, further experiments were carried out at 180 min as a significant contact time for Zn^{II} adsorption.

Effect of biosorbent dose :

Fig. 3 illustrates the variation of adsorption efficiency with varying adsorbent dosage using *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum*, which shows that the adsorption efficiency increases with an increase in adsorbent dosage. A graph was plotted between the different dosage of biosorbent *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* and the resultant percentage removal of Zn^{II}. The effect of different biosorbent dosage (2–10 g/100 mL) with percentage removal of zinc is shown in Fig. 3. The graph

Fig. 1. Effect of solution pH on biosorption of Zn^{II} by *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* ($C_0 = 100$ ppm, dosage = 2 g/100 ml, contact time = 180 min).

Fig. 2. Effect of contact time on biosorption for Zn^{II} by *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* ($C_0 = 100$ ppm, dosage = 2 g/100 ml).

Fig. 3. Effect of biosorbent dose on biosorption capacity of Zn^{II} ($C_0 = 100$ mg/100 ml, contact time = 180 min).

shows a marginal increase in Zn^{II} removal with increasing biomass concentration.

Effect of initial metal concentration :

The biosorption capacity of *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* as a function of the initial concentrations of Zn^{II} have been studied at different concentrations of Zn^{II} in batch experiments. Increasing the initial concentration of Zn^{II} in a batch study resulted in decreasing percentage of Zn^{II} removal because evidently the biosorbent was approaching its saturation uptake capacity. Fig. 4 shows that, batch adsorption study using *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* biomass percentage

removal of Zn^{II} decreased from 87.12 to 40.23 and 68.52 to 24.54 when the initial concentration of Zn^{II} was increased from 100 to 1000 mg/L.

Effect of temperature :

Fig. 5 shows the biosorption of Zn^{II} for varied temperatures at 180 min of contact time. As shown in Fig. 5 biosorption capacities at 20 °C, 30 °C, 40 °C and 60 °C were found Zn^{II} as 61.03, 71.17, 87.12, 58.24 mg/100 mL for *Carissa carandas* and 54.53, 65.91, 68.52, 49.12 mg/100 mL for *Syzygium aromaticum* respectively. It was observed that the biosorption capacity of *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* decreased over

Fig. 4. Effect of initial metal concentration on biosorption of Zn^{II} (dosage = 2 g/100 ml, contact time = 180 min, pH = 6, T = 300 K).

Fig. 5. Effect of temperature on biosorption of Zn^{II} ($C_0 = 100$ ppm, dosage = 2 g/100 ml, contact time = 180 min).

40 °C for zinc. The decrease in biosorption capacity of *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* above 40 °C for zinc may be attributed to the deactivation of the biosorbent surface or the destruction of some active sites on the biosorbent surface. As a result, the optimum temperature for Zn^{II} biosorption was chosen as 40 °C for subsequent experiments.

Isothermal studies :

Adsorption isotherms describe how the adsorbate interacts with adsorbent and show the comprehensive information about the nature of interaction¹⁸. The analysis of the isotherm data by fitting them to different isotherm models is an important step to get information on the surface properties of the adsorbents and its affinity with zinc. Find the suitable model that can be used for design purpose. In this research, biosorption isotherm study was carried out on two well-known two-parameter isotherms : Langmuir and Freundlich. The well-known expression of Langmuir isotherm¹⁹ model is presented as

$$q_e = \frac{Q_0 b C_e}{1 + b C_e} \quad (1)$$

where, C_e (mg/L) and q_e (mg/g) are the liquid phase concentration and solid phase concentration of adsorbate at

equilibrium, respectively and Q_0 (mg/g) and b (L/mg) are the Langmuir isotherm constants.

According to Kratochvil and Volesky²⁰ high Q_0 and b values correspond to good quality biosorbents. High values of b can be seen in an isotherm with a steep initial slope, indicating a high affinity of the sorbate for the sorbent.

The well-known expression for the Freundlich isotherm model²¹ is given as :

$$q_e = K_F C_e^n \quad (2)$$

where, K_F [$\text{mg/g (L/g)}^{1/n}$] is the Freundlich constant related to the bonding energy, n is the heterogeneity factor which depicts the extent of deviation from linearity of the adsorption. It indicates the degree of non-linearity between solution concentration and adsorption.

Table 1 lists the calculated Freundlich and Langmuir isotherm constants. Based on regression coefficient (R^2) values which are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7, the experimental data for adsorption of Zn^{II} onto *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* powder indicate that the Langmuir adsorption isotherm shows a better fit with the

Table 1. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm constants for Zn^{II} ion biosorption

Adsorbent	Langmuir isotherm			Freundlich isotherm		
	q_{max}	K_L	R^2	K_F	N	R^2
<i>Carissa carandas</i>	1.031	969	0.99	0.614	1.51	0.99
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	0.821	609	0.99	0.68	1.68	0.93

experimental data observed in this study compared with the Freundlich isotherm.

As shown in Fig. 7 the maximum adsorption capacities (q_{max}) estimated from the Langmuir isotherm model for Zn^{II} were 1.031 mg/g and 0.821 mg/g for *Carissa carandas* leaves and *Syzygium aromaticum* respectively.

as either mass transfer or chemical reaction in order to obtain the optimum operating conditions for industrial-scale batch processes. In batch systems, adsorption kinetics is described by a number of models based on adsorption equilibrium such as the pseudo-first order and the pseudo-second order kinetic models. The linearized pseudo-first order kinetic model takes the following form :

$$q_t = q_e - q_e \exp(-K_1 t) \tag{3}$$

$$\log(q_e - q) = \log q_e - \frac{K_1}{2.303} t \tag{4}$$

where q is the amount of (mg/g) at time t (min), q_e is the amount of adsorbed at equilibrium (mg/g) and K_1 is the

Fig. 6. Freundlich isotherm for (a) *Carissa carandas* and (b) *Syzygium aromaticum* for zinc(II).

Fig. 7. Langmuir isotherm for (a) *Carissa carandas* and (b) *Syzygium aromaticum* for zinc(II).

Adsorption kinetics

Kinetic study provides valuable information about the mechanism of adsorption and subsequently investigation of the controlling mechanism of the biosorption process

equilibrium rate constant of pseudo-first order adsorption (min^{-1}). The plot of $\log(q_e - q_t)$ versus t gave a straight line for the first order adsorption kinetics.

The pseudo-second order kinetic model considered in

this study is given as :

$$\frac{1}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (5)$$

where K_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$) is the second order reaction rate constant.

The experimental data and the parameters of both models are tabulated in Table 2. It is obvious that the coefficient of correlation ($R^2 : 0.99$) for the pseudo-second order kinetic model is higher in comparison with the pseudo-first order kinetic model and the calculated value of q_e for the pseudo-second order kinetic model is very close to the experimental value. Similar experimental results indicate that the pseudo-second order kinetic model fits the equilibrium data for biosorption of Zn^{II} on *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* from aqueous solutions quite well.

SEM images

The SEM images of adsorbents before and after adsorption are given in Figs. 8 and 9 respectively for *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum*. From these images, it is clear that there is significant difference in the appearance of the adsorbent surfaces. Images clearly highlight the action of adsorption on the surfaces of both the adsorbents and strengthen the view point of the researchers. Figs. 8 and 9 show the SEM images before biosorption and after biosorption on *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* respectively, which show that surface of biosorbents having sufficient space to grab metal ions in the voids, which seem occupied in the images after biosorption, indicates that surface of biosorbents after adsorption are smoother than surface of biosorbent before biosorption. This phenomena happened because the metal ions are filled in pores of biosorbents surface.

Table 2. Kinetics studies of biosorption of Zn^{II} on *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum*

Biosorbent	Metal ion concentration (ppm)	Pseudo-first order kinetic model			Pseudo-second order kinetic model		
		$q_{e,cal}$ (mg/g)	K_1 (min^{-1})	R^2	$q_{e,cal}$ (mg/g)	K_2 ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	R^2
<i>Carissa carandas</i>	100	40.04	4.8×10^{-3}	0.91	113.63	1.5×10^{-4}	0.99
	300	90.01	3.6×10^{-3}	0.95	212.76	1.1×10^{-4}	0.99
	500	170.71	2.0×10^{-3}	0.96	263.15	1.9×10^{-4}	0.99
	700	252.14	1.1×10^{-3}	0.92	322.58	2.6×10^{-4}	0.99
	1000	290.03	1.84×10^{-3}	0.96	434.78	1.3×10^{-4}	0.99
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	100	34.46	4.1×10^{-3}	0.89	82.64	2.6×10^{-4}	0.99
	300	108.85	2.5×10^{-3}	0.86	181.81	2.5×10^{-4}	0.99
	500	181.27	9.2×10^{-3}	0.93	222.22	5.2×10^{-4}	0.99
	700	225.87	9.21×10^{-3}	0.95	277.77	4.4×10^{-4}	0.99
	1000	196.36	1.3×10^{-3}	0.95	256.41	3.2×10^{-4}	0.99

Fig. 8. SEM image of *Carissa carandas* : (a) before adsorption; (b) after adsorption of Zn^{II} .

Fig. 9. SEM image of *Syzygium aromaticum* : (a) before adsorption; (b) after adsorption of Zn^{II}.

Conclusions

This study is focused on the biosorption of zinc(II) ion onto of *Carissa carandas* and *Syzygium aromaticum* biomass from aqueous solution. The operating parameters, pH of solution, biomass dosage, contact time, initial metal ion concentration, and temperature are effective on the biosorption efficiency of zinc(II). Biosorbent *Carissa carandas* leaf powder showed higher sorption efficiency than that of biosorbent *Syzygium aromaticum* powder under identical experimental conditions. Also, the adsorption of zinc(II) onto *Carissa carandas* was best described by the Freundlich isotherm model.

However, we suggest that it is also necessary to investigate the efficacy of *Carissa carandas* leaves powder to treat real industrial effluents. There is a ready supply of agricultural wastes worldwide. The use of such materials will not only convert into low-cost effective adsorbents, but also provide a green solution to their disposal.

Since, several parameters including migration of metal ions from bulk solution to the surface of the adsorbent through bulk diffusion and the adsorption of metal ions at an active site on the surface of the adsorbent by chemical reactions play very important role in deciding the adsorption kinetics and adsorption mechanism; the actual adsorption mechanism is yet to be discussed and explained.

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